

Digital Building Permit: analysis and creation of rules to automate the process

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Abstract

Design approval in municipalities is a fundamental part of project development. It is during this phase that the project's feasibility and potential modifications for the construction stage are determined. Urban requirements, such as building setbacks from lot boundaries and maximum construction areas, are essential for project approval. Despite this, research on the digitalization of this process is still in development, with few implementation examples.

The increasing use of Building Information Modeling (BIM), particularly with the IFC schema, presents a consistent path forward. The use of BIM for checking project requirements is commonly referred to in the literature as code checking and validation or Automated Compliance Checking (ACC), while the verification of requirements for municipal project approval is known as Digital Building Permit (DBP).

This study aims to analyze building codes and understand the opportunities and constraints involved in translating them into machine-readable language. The experimental phase will encompass the analysis and transcription of codes into conceptual models that can be read

by information systems, as well as the insertion of numerical limits into a project analysis software, CYPEURBAN.

The presented results include an analysis of the possible limits of computerization of urban codes, a presentation on the Level of Information Need for the IFC entities involved in the checking process, and modeling guidelines to achieve it.

Dissertation:

Link for full text

Presentation video:

<https://youtu.be/3b4sPkoWTIs>

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